

Nickel and copper complexes of a pyridyl-appended tetra-amide ligand : Syntheses and characterization[†]

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Abstract : This work presents the synthesis and characterization of Ni²⁺ (1) and Cu²⁺ (2) complexes of a tetra-amide ligand containing appended 3-pyridyl rings. Both complexes have been crystallographically characterized and exhibit a square-planar geometry around the metal ion. Both complexes display an interesting solid-state packing between complex anions and Na⁺ ions involving O_{amide} groups and appended 3-pyridyl rings generating sheet-like architectures. Cyclic voltammetric studies were performed to understand the redox nature of complexes 1 and 2 whereas one-electron electrochemical oxidation led to the generation of unstable 1^{Ox} and 2^{Ox} species displaying unique absorption spectral features.

Keywords : Tetra-amide ligand, nickel, copper, crystal structures, electrochemistry.

Introduction

The coordination chemistry of amide-based ligands is of considerable interest due to several reasons. First, amide-based ligands tend to produce stable metal complexes due to the involvement of anionic *N*-amidate in bonding¹. Second, such ligands in their anionic form have the propensity to stabilize a metal ion in its higher oxidation state(s) due to strong σ donation². Third, such ligands have been effectively used to provide coordinations to metals in various oxidation chemistry reactions³. Fourth, *N*-amidate donation has also been identified in several metallo-proteins and metallo-enzymes⁴. Some of these factors have resulted in tremendous growth in the coordination chemistry with amide-based ligands¹⁻³. Collins and co-workers^{2,5} have epitomized the utilization of tetra-anionic amide-based macrocyclic frameworks to showcase a rich coordination and oxidation chemistry. Journaux and co-workers⁶ have also utilized tetra-anionic amide-based ligands to exhibit a wealthy coordination and substrate oxidation chemistry. Our group has been interested in understanding the ligand architectural parameters that not only affect the structural criteria but also the redox properties. Over a period of time, we have shown several amide-based macrocyclic⁷ as well as analogous open-chain ligands⁸ to illustrate their affluent coordination chemistry with assorted transition metals. Interestingly, there have

been considerably a very few reports to incorporate a tetra-anionic coordination within a non-macrocyclic ligand framework. Recently, we have illustrated a unique strategy to create a tetra-anionic coordination site by incorporating *N*-pyrrolate⁹ or *N*-indolate¹⁰ functional groups in addition to *N*-amidate donors. Such tetra-anionic ligands resulted in the stabilization and/or isolation of metal ions in their higher oxidation state⁹. In this work, we present an interesting multidentate ligand (H₄L^{3py}) capable of providing tetra-anionic *N*-amidate coordinations to a metal ion. The ligand is further decorated with appended 3-pyridyl rings that could be involved in holding additional metal ion(s) therefore opening up the possibility to generate unprecedented heterometallic complexes and/or networks. Herein, we present our preliminary findings with such a ligand by depicting the coordination of a metal ion within tetra-anionic N₄ coordination sphere while also illustrating the coordinating abilities of the appended 3-pyridyl rings.

[†]In honour of Professor Animesh Chakravorty on the occasion of his 80th birth anniversary.

Experimental

Materials :

Ortho-phenylenediamine (Thomas Baker), ethyl chlorooxoacetate (Sigma-Aldrich), 3-aminopyridine (Sigma-Aldrich), and triphenylphosphite (Sigma-Aldrich) were used as received. Solvents were dried and/or purified as per the standard literature methods¹¹.

Synthesis :

Diethyl-2,2'-(1,2-phenylenebis(azanediyl))bis(2-oxoacetate), H_2L^{ester} (A) : To a solution of *ortho*-phenylenediamine (1.0 g, 0.009 mol) in dry THF (50 ml) was added triethylamine (2.048 g, 0.0202 mol) and the mixture was stirred for 30 min at room temperature. The reaction mixture was cooled on ice bath followed by the drop-wise addition of ethylchlorooxoacetate (2.525 g, 0.0184 mol) while stirring. Addition resulted in an immediate precipitation of a white solid (Et_3NCl) which was filtered. Subsequently, THF was removed under the reduced pressure to afford an oily product. This oily product was triturated with cold water resulting in the formation of a pale yellow product. Finally this product was washed with 5% aqueous methanol (20 ml) followed by diethyl ether and dried under vacuum. Yield : 2.5 g (88%). Selected FT-IR bands (KBr, ν cm^{-1}) : 3256 (NH), 1760 and 1687 (C=O). 1H NMR spectrum (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 9.49 (2H, s), 7.57 (2H, dd, J 7.3, 3.6 Hz), 7.24 (2H, dd, J 6.1, 3.5 Hz), 4.32 (4H, q, J 7.2 Hz), 1.34 (6H, t, J 7.1 Hz).

2,2'-(1,2-Phenylenebis(azanediyl))bis(2-oxoacetic acid), H_2L^{COOH} (B) : H_2L^{ester} (1.0 g, 0.0032 mol) was dissolved in a mixture of THF- H_2O (1 : 1, v/v) and to this solid NaOH (0.324 g, 0.0081 mol) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred for 4 h at room temperature followed by the removal of THF under the reduced pressure. The resulting aqueous solution was treated with dropwise addition of 2 *N* HCl. The addition of HCl was monitored with the help of pH paper strips. The acidified solution (pH ~ 4) was stored at 5 °C overnight resulting in the precipitation of a white crystalline compound. The white product was isolated by filtration and dried under vacuum. Yield : 0.55 g (67%). Selected FT-IR bands (KBr, ν cm^{-1}) : 3300 and 3246 (NH), 1774 and 1675 (C=O), 3453 (-OH (acid)). 1H NMR spectrum (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6), δ : 10.33 (2H, s), 7.55 (2H, dd, J 6.0, 3.6 Hz), 7.24 (2H, dd, J 6.1, 3.5 Hz). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 162.256 (C_1), 157.386 (C_2), 130.237 (C_3), 126.682 (C_4), 126.035 (C_5) ppm.

$N^1, N^{1'}-(1,2-Phenylene)bis(N^2-(pyridin-3-yl)oxalamide)$, H_4L^{3py} : A suspension of H_2L^{COOH} (0.5 g, 0.0017 mol) and 3-aminopyridine (0.33 g, 0.0035 mol) in pyridine (20 ml) was stirred at 100 °C for 30 min. Triphenylphosphite (1.161 g, 0.0037 mol) was added dropwise and the solution was further stirred for 6 h at 100 °C. After cooling to room temperature, pyridine was removed under the reduced pressure. The oily remains were triturated with cold MeOH that resulted in a white powder. Yield : 0.62 g (86%). Selected FT-IR bands (Zn-Se ATR, ν cm^{-1}) : 3280 (NH), 1683 and 1662 (C=O). 1H NMR spectrum (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 11.12 (2H, s), 10.69 (2H, s), 8.98 (2H, d, J 2.0 Hz), 8.32 (2H, d, J 4.3 Hz), 8.19 (2H, dd, J 9.3, 2.7 Hz), 7.65 (2H, dd, J 6.0, 3.6 Hz), 7.38 (2H, dd, J 8.3, 4.8 Hz), 7.31 (2H, dd, J 5.9, 3.6 Hz). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 159.32 (C_4), 158.86 (C_5), 146.06 (C_9), 142.77 (C_{10}), 134.84 (C_3), 130.40 (C_6), 129.90 (C_7), 128.31 (C_8), 126.92 (C_2), 115.73 (C_1).

$Na_2[NiL^{3py}]$ (1) : Ligand H_4L^{3py} (0.2 g, 0.494 mmol) was taken in MeOH (10 ml) followed by the addition of solid NaOH (0.082 g, 2.074 mmol). The resulting mixture was stirred for 30 min. To the resultant clear solution, a solution of $NiCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (0.117 g, 0.494 mmol) dissolved in MeOH (5 ml) was added resulting in the generation of an orange coloured solution. The reaction mixture was finally stirred for 2 h. The reaction was concentrated to its half volume and filtered through a pad of celite in a medium porosity frit. The vapours of diethyl ether were diffused to the filtrate that resulted in dark orange crystals within a day which were isolated and dried under vacuum. Yield : 0.098 g (78%). Anal. Calcd. for $C_{21}H_{18}N_6Na_2NiO_6$ ($Na_2[NiL^{3py}] \cdot MeOH \cdot H_2O$) : C, 45.44; H, 3.27; N, 15.14. Found : C, 46.02; H, 3.14; N, 15.42%. Selected FT-IR bands (Zn-Se ATR, ν cm^{-1}) : 1624 and 1592 (C=O). Conductivity (DMF ~ 1 mM solution, 298 K) : $\Lambda_M = 155 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$ (the range for 1 : 2 electrolyte in DMF is 130–170). Absorption spectrum [λ_{max} , nm, DMF (ϵ , $M^{-1} cm^{-1}$)] : 520 (1930). 1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 8.05 (2H, dd, J 5.9, 3.4 Hz), 7.95 (2H, d, J 2.2 Hz), 7.66 (2H, d, J 6.0 Hz), 6.88 (2H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 6.63 (2H, dd, J 5.9, 3.4 Hz), 6.47 (2H, dd, J 7.9, 4.7 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 169.56 (C_4), 164.28 (C_5), 148.94 (C_6), 143.64 (C_9), 142.90 (C_{10}), 142.63 (C_3), 133.65 (C_8), 122.38 (C_1), 122.02 (C_7), 119.38 (C_2) ppm.

$\text{Na}_2[\text{CuL}^{3\text{py}}]$ (**2**) : Complex **2** was synthesised in a similar manner as mentioned for **1** with the following reagents : $\text{H}_4\text{L}^{3\text{py}}$ (0.2 g, 0.494 mmol), NaOH (0.082 g, 2.074 mmol) and $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.084 g, 0.494 mmol). The product was isolated as a brown crystalline material. Yield : 0.085 g (68 %). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_6\text{Na}_2\text{CuO}_8$ ($\text{Na}_2[\text{CuL}^{3\text{py}}] \cdot 2\text{MeOH} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) : C, 43.32; H, 3.97; N, 13.78. Found : C, 43.02; H, 4.05; N, 13.84%. Selected FT-IR bands (Zn-Se, $\nu \text{ cm}^{-1}$) : 1600 and 1573 (C=O). Conductivity (DMF ~ 1 mM solution, 298 K) : $\Lambda_{\text{M}} = 160 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ (the range for 1 : 1 electrolyte in DMF is 130–170). Absorption spectrum [λ_{max} , nm, DMF (ϵ , $\text{M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)] : 523 (365).

Physical measurements :

The conductivity measurements were done in DMF using the digital conductivity bridge from Popular Traders, India (Model number : PT-825). The elemental analysis data were obtained from Elementar Analysensysteme GmbH Vario EL-III instrument. The NMR measurements were done using Jeol (400 MHz) instrument using TMS as an internal standard. The infra-red spectra either as KBr pellet or as Zn-Se ATR were recorded using the Perkin-Elmer FT-IR 2000 or Perkin-Elmer Spectrum-Two (Zn-Se, ATR) spectrometer, respectively. The absorption spectra were recorded using the Perkin-Elmer Lambda-25 spectrophotometer.

Cyclic voltammetry :

The cyclic voltammetric experiments were performed using a CH Instruments electrochemical analyzer (Model 1120 A). The cell contained a glassy-carbon or a Pt working electrode, a Pt wire auxiliary electrode, and a Ag/AgCl as the reference electrode¹². Although, Ag/AgCl reference electrode was used; the potentials were converted to the saturated calomel electrode (SCE) throughout the text¹³. For coulometric experiments, a Pt mesh was used as the working electrode. The solutions were ~ 1 mM in complex and ~ 0.1 M in supporting electrolyte, TBAP (tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate). Under our experimental condition, the $E_{1/2}$ value (in Volts) for the couple Fc^+/Fc was observed at 0.47 V in DMF vs SCE¹³.

X-Ray crystallography :

Single crystals suitable for the X-ray diffraction studies of complexes **1** and **2** were grown by the slow diffusion of diethyl ether to a MeOH solution of compound at

room temperature. X-Ray diffraction data were collected at 298 K either using Bruker Kappa Apex-CCD diffractometer^{14,15} or an Oxford XCalibur CCD diffractometer¹⁶ using MoK α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). The structures were solved by the direct methods using SIR-92¹⁷ and refined by the full-matrix least-squares method on F^2 (SHELXL-97)¹⁸. All calculations were carried out using the WinGX crystallographic package¹⁹. The non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically whereas the hydrogen atoms were fixed at the calculated positions. For complex **2**, bond distance between the carbon atom C23 and oxygen atom O8 was fixed by applying restraints. Hydrogen atoms coordinated to water molecules O1w and O2w for complexes **1** and **2** respectively and MeOH oxygen atoms O6 and O8 in complex **1** and **2** respectively could not be located. However, these hydrogen atoms have been included in the molecular formula. The crystallographic data collection and structure refinement parameters for both complexes are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Crystallographic data collection and structure refinement parameters for complexes **1** and **2**

	1	2
Empirical formula	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_6\text{Na}_2\text{NiO}_6$	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{24}\text{CuN}_6\text{Na}_2\text{O}_8$
Formula mass	555.10	609.99
Crystal system	Triclinic	Triclinic
Space group	<i>P</i> -1	<i>P</i> -1
<i>a</i> (Å)	10.1887(2)	11.201(5)
<i>b</i> (Å)	10.949(2)	11.658(5)
<i>c</i> (Å)	12.044(3)	11.865(5)
α (deg)	98.769(16)	67.415(5)
β (deg)	96.684(16)	62.678(5)
γ (deg)	113.998(18)	69.346(5)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1189.1(4)	1241.2(9)
<i>Z</i>	2	2
$D_{\text{calcd.}}$ (mg m ⁻³)	1.550	1.632
<i>F</i> (000)	568	626
<i>T</i> (K)	298	298
ν (mm ⁻¹)	0.903	0.976
Final <i>R</i> indices	$R_1 = 0.1016,$	$R_1 = 0.0341,$
$[I > 2\sigma(I)]^{a,b}$	$wR_2 = 0.2670$	$wR_2 = 0.0913$
<i>R</i> indices (all data)	$R_1 = 0.1199,$	$R_1 = 0.0401,$
	$wR_2 = 0.2824$	$wR_2 = 0.0939$
GOF ^c	1.134	1.089
^a $R = \sum(F_o - F_c) / \sum F_o ,$ ^b $wR = \{\sum[w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2] / \sum[w(F_o^2)^2]\}^{1/2}.$		

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization of ligand and complexes :

The ligand H_4L^{3py} was designed to provide four anionic N_{amide} coordination sites to a metal ion within the basal plane. This ligand was synthesised in three steps as shown in Scheme 1. In the first step, *ortho*-phenylenediamine was coupled with ethylchlorooxoacetate to produce the ester **A**. The second step involved base assisted

Scheme 1. Reaction pathway for the synthesis of ligand H_4L^{3py} .

hydrolysis of ester **A** producing intermediate **B** with free acid groups. In the final step, ligand H_4L^{3py} was obtained by the coupling of **B** with 3-aminopyridine in pyridine using $P(OPh)_3$. The ligand H_4L^{3py} , isolated in 86% yield, was characterized with various spectroscopic techniques (Figs. S1-S5, Supplementary data).

The nickel and copper complexes, **1** and **2**, were synthesized by treating H_4L^{3py} in its deprotonated form $[L^{3py}]^{4-}$ with MCl_2 salt in MeOH. (Scheme 2). Highly crystalline products were obtained by the vapour diffusion of diethyl ether to a MeOH solution of compounds. Complexes **1** and **2** were obtained as the deep orange and deep brown crystalline product, respectively. FT-IR spectra of both complexes exhibited the disappearance of ν_{NH} stretches and bathochromic shifted $\nu_{C=O}$ stretches by *ca.* 60 cm^{-1} when compared to free ligand. Both these observations suggest the coordination of metal ion via deprotonated N_{amide} groups²⁰. The conductivity measurement displays a 1 : 2 electrolytic nature for both the complexes²¹. The absorption spectrum of complex **1** in DMF exhibits λ_{max} at 520 nm (Fig. 1). For complex **1**, $d^8 Ni^{2+}$

ion is in a square-planar environment and thus three transitions from four lower fully occupied d -orbitals to the upper empty d -orbital are expected^{7a-c,22}. However, in case of high square-planar ligand field strength and the involvement of only metal-ligand σ bonding, such four lower-lying metal $3d$ orbitals are usually so close in energy that individual transitions from them to the upper empty $3d$ orbital are not distinguishable and rather a broad feature is usually noted as the case in **16**,^{7a-c,22}. On the other hand, Cu^{II} complex **2** displays a broad feature at *ca.* 550 nm with low extinction coefficient (Fig. 1). Such a low-energy $d-d$ transition is typically observed for square-planar to tetragonally distorted geometries and is actually consists of three individual transitions (i.e. ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_{1g}$ in D_{4h} symmetry^{7d,23}).

Scheme 2. Preparative route for the synthesis of metal complexes.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of complexes **1** and **2** recorded in DMF.

Taking advantage of the diamagnetic nature of nickel complex, **1** was further characterized by the NMR spectroscopy. The proton NMR spectrum exhibits sharp features for the phenylene as well as 3-pyridyl ring protons (Fig. 2). In particular, ring protons were noted as either double doublets or multiplets with coupling constants varying between 2–8 Hz. Notably, proton NMR spectrum also displays the signals for Na-bound MeOH mole-

Fig. 2. ^1H NMR spectrum of complex **1** recorded in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$. The residual solvent and adventitious water peaks are marked by asterisk.

cule as was noted crystallographically (*vide infra*). The ^{13}C NMR spectrum of **1** displays 10 signals for 10 chemically different carbon centers. For example, two amidic carbon centers (C4 and C5) were found to resonate at *ca.* 164 and *ca.* 170 ppm, respectively (Fig. S6, Supplementary data). The ^{13}C NMR spectrum further asserts the presence of Na-bound MeOH molecule by displaying a signal at *ca.* 48 ppm for its $-\text{CH}_3$ group.

Crystal structure studies :

Both nickel (**1**) and copper (**2**) complexes were crystallographically characterized. The molecular structures of the anionic part are shown in Fig. 3 whereas the selected bonding parameters are presented in Table 2. In both complexes, metal ion, Ni^{2+} in **1** and Cu^{2+} in **2**, is

Fig. 3. Crystal structures of nickel (**1**) and copper (**2**) complexes. Thermal ellipsoids are drawn at 30% probability whereas hydrogen atoms, sodium ions, and lattice solvent molecules are omitted for clarity.

Table 2. Selected bond lengths (\AA) and bond angles ($^\circ$) for complexes **1** and **2**

	1	2
M-N1	1.838(6)	1.933(3)
M-N2	1.852(6)	1.929(3)
M-N3	1.923(5)	1.974(3)
M-N4	1.941(6)	1.974(3)
Na2-N5	2.549(9)	2.558(4)
N2-M-N1	83.5(2)	82.76(13)
N2-M-N3	84.7(2)	82.97(12)
N1-M-N3	168.2(2)	165.32(13)
N2-M-N4	167.7(2)	165.75(12)
N1-M-N4	84.2(2)	83.03(12)
N3-M-N4	107.6(2)	111.28(12)

coordinated by four anionic $\text{N}_{\text{amidate}}$ groups in the basal plane. Both complexes display nearly square-planar geometry with τ_4 value being 0.17 for **1** and 0.20 for **2**²⁴. For reference, τ_4 has standard values of 0 and 1 for perfect square-planar and tetrahedral geometries, respectively²⁴. Further, nickel and copper atoms are marginally displaced by 0.118 \AA and 0.169 \AA , respectively from the N_4 basal plane. For both complexes, five-membered chelate rings make angles with the metal ion lower than 90° therefore suggesting a tight chelation. For complexes **1** and **2**, average $\text{M-N}_{\text{amide}}$ bond distances were found to be *ca.* 1.889 \AA and 1.953 \AA , respectively. A comparison of two complexes exhibits that the ligand makes stronger bonds by 0.064 \AA with the Ni^{II} ion than that of Cu^{II} ion. Interestingly, $\text{M-N}_{\text{amide}}$ bond distances involving pyridyl rings were longer as compared to $\text{M-N}_{\text{amide}}$ bonds involving phenylene ring.

Notably, the appended 3-pyridyl rings in complexes **1** and **2** were found to align nearly perpendicular to the plane created by the metal-based N_4 coordination sphere. For example, pyridyl ring containing atom N6 was observed to make an angle of *ca.* 70° in **1** and *ca.* 65° in **2**. Similarly, plane involving pyridyl ring with atom N5 makes an angle of *ca.* 71° in **1** and *ca.* 69° in **2**. Interestingly, in case of complex **1**, both 3-pyridyl rings are oriented in opposite direction whereas in case of **2** both the 3-pyridyl rings are aligned in the same direction.

For complex **1**, the asymmetric unit cell consists of one tetra-amide ligand, one Ni^{II} ion, two Na^+ ions, one water, and one MeOH (Fig. 4a). While the Ni^{II} ion is coordinated within the N_4 ligand cavity; Na^+ ions are ligated to the O_{amide} groups. Notably, Na1 atom is further coordinated by a water (O1w) and a methanol (O6)

molecule. The black arrows indicate the involvement of the respective atoms in extending the coordination sphere. For example, O_{amide} atom O4 coordinates to both Na1 and Na2 ions. Further, two complex anionic units are linked to each other involving both sodium ions, Na1 and Na2, to form a dimer as shown in Fig. 4b. Importantly, repetition of such a bonding pattern results in the generation of a one-dimension (1D) double chain. More importantly, one of the appended 3-pyridyl rings plays a crucial role in connecting the resultant double chains together. In particular, Na2 ion coordinates to the appended 3-pyridyl ring having N5 atom and as a result a two-dimensional (2D) sheet-like structure is generated (Fig. 4c).

Fig. 4. Different views of the crystal structure of complex 1. (a) Asymmetric unit cell of complex 1. (b) A dinuclear unit due to the coordination between complex anions and sodium ions. (c) An extended view along the *c* axis.

In case of complex 2, the asymmetric unit is comprised of one tetra-amide ligand, one Cu^{II} ion, two Na^+ ions, two water, and two MeOH molecules (Fig. 5a). In Fig. 5a, black arrows depict the involvement of the respective atoms in extending the coordination sphere. The tetradentate ligand houses the Cu^{II} ion within its N_4 cavity whereas Na^+ ions are coordinated by O_{amide} atoms in addition to water and MeOH molecules. In particular, Na1 ion is coordinated by O_{amide} atoms O3 and O4, water O2w, and MeOH O8 while O1w and O6_{MeOH} additionally bridge with Na2 atom. On the other hand, Na2 ion receives coordinations from O1_{amide} and N5_{pyridine} whereas O1w, O4_{amide}, and O6_{MeOH} provide bridging coordination environment. The consequence of O_{amide} bonding to the sodium ions results in the formation of a dimeric unit as shown in Fig. 5b. Such dimeric unit based double chains propagate in *c* direction and are further connected to each other via $Na \cdots N_{pyridyl}$ synthons to generate a 2D sheet (Fig. 5c).

Fig. 5. Different views of the crystal structure of complex 2. (a) Asymmetric unit cell of complex 2. (b) A dinuclear unit due to the coordination between complex anions and sodium ions. (c) An extended view along the *b* axis.

It is noteworthy to mention that the manner in which sodium ions are involved in coordination to the complex anions strongly suggest the possibility of incorporating other metal ions (such as transition or lanthanide ions) for the design and synthesis of extended structures involving magnetically significant centers.

Cyclic voltammetric studies :

In order to investigate the redox properties of complexes **1** and **2**, cyclic voltammetric studies were performed in DMF (Fig. 6 and S7, Supplementary data). Both complexes exhibit reversible M^{3+}/M^{2+} redox responses (E_1) in the positive potential range. For complex **1**, the E_1 redox couple was observed at 0.35 V with peak-to-peak separation (ΔE_p) of 70 mV. In case of complex **2**, the E_1 redox couple was observed at 0.23 V with peak-to-peak separation of 100 mV. Both E_1 redox responses were one-electron in nature as confirmed by the coulometric studies. Interestingly, Ni^{3+}/Ni^{2+} redox couple was noted to be 120 mV more positive when compared to the Cu^{3+}/Cu^{2+} couple. Such a stark difference suggests that the tetra-amide ligand-based cavity is ideally suited to support the +2 oxidation state more favorable in case of nickel ion. In other words, tetra-anionic ligand is more likely to favor +3 oxidation state for copper ion than that of nickel.

Fig. 6. Cyclic voltammograms of complexes **1** and **2** in DMF at a platinum working electrode. Scan rate : 100 mV s⁻¹; supporting electrolyte : 0.1 M TBAP.

In addition to M^{3+}/M^{2+} redox responses, both complexes also exhibited irreversible oxidative responses (E_{pa}) at a much higher positive potentials (*ca.* 1.0 V) (Fig. S7, Supplementary data). We believe that such an oxidative

redox response corresponds to the ligand-centered oxidation located at the *o*-benzenediamidate fragment, generating the M^{3+} -*ortho*-benzosemiquinonediimine π -cation species. Such an assignment has been made based on our earlier nickel and copper complexes of various amide-based ligands⁷⁻¹⁰ while further supported with literature precedents^{6,22}.

We then attempted to compare the M^{3+}/M^{2+} redox potentials (E_1) of the present complexes with other reported complexes supported with open-chain ligands offering N₄ coordination environment (Chart 1). As evident, the M^{3+}/M^{2+} redox potentials for **1** and **2** are on the higher side when compared to the tetra-amidate complexes **A** and **B**^{6a,22a}; amide-imidazole based Ni²⁺ complex **C**²⁵; Ni²⁺ and Cu²⁺ complexes **D** and **E** supported with amide-pyrrole based ligands^{9b}. However, M^{3+}/M^{2+} redox potentials are somewhat comparable to complexes **F** and **G** having amide-indole ligands^{10b}. Furthermore,

Chart 1. Chemical structures of assorted Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes supported with N₄ ligand systems and their M^{3+}/M^{2+} redox potentials (vs SCE).

incorporation of substituted amine or quinolone functional groups in bis-amide based ligands makes the M^{3+}/M^{2+} redox potentials quite positive as can be seen with com-

plexes **H**^{8a} and **I**²⁶. Such a comparison of redox potentials nicely depicts the sensitivity of M^{3+}/M^{2+} couple over the selection of donor groups along with two anionic N-amidate donors. The potentials are typically more negative for the ligands capable of providing tetra-anionic than di-anionic coordination environment about the metal ion.

Electrochemical oxidation :

The accessible M^{3+}/M^{2+} redox responses and their reversibility suggest that complexes **1** and **2** may further be oxidized. Subsequently, both nickel and copper complexes were subjected to one-electron controlled potential oxidation in DMF. In case of complex **1**, one-electron oxidation resulted in color change from the original orange to brown. The absorption spectrum of the oxidized species, **1**^{Ox}, exhibited spectral features at 940 nm, 600 nm, and 525 nm (Fig. 7). The molar extinction coefficient values for these transitions were in the range of 550–1200 $M^{-1} cm^{-1}$. Importantly, such spectral features are quite similar to our earlier Ni^{III} species supported with 12-membered and 13-membered macrocyclic ligands^{7a-d}. In fact, our earlier detailed spectroscopic studies

Fig. 7. Absorption spectrum of one-electron electrochemically oxidized species **1**^{Ox} (red trace) and its comparison with complex **1** (black trace). Both spectra were recorded in DMF. See the text for details.

have concluded the stabilization of a M^{3+} species within a square-planar coordination environment^{7a-d}. Based on such a fact, we tentatively suggest that such spectral features are ligand-to-metal charge transfer in nature^{7a-d,22}. Further, low energy of these transitions suggest a small energy difference between the ground and excited states with considerable overlap of $d\pi$ - $p\pi$ orbitals^{6,7a-d,22}. Similarly, copper complex (**2**) on one-electron coulometric oxidation generated an intense deep-brown species, **2**^{Ox}, with a broad band in far IR region with λ_{max} at ca. 1100 nm ($\epsilon = 350 M^{-1} cm^{-1}$) (Fig. 8). The observation of such

a low-energy band is quite intriguing and suggests the involvement of low-lying orbitals in the electronic transition^{6,7a-d,22}. We tentatively suggest that one-electron oxidation has generated a Cu^{II} -Ligand(•) radical species that is responsible for the observation of 1100 nm transition. In addition, there were other obscure broad features between 500–650 nm.

Interestingly, species **2**^{Ox} was relatively much more unstable than that of **1**^{Ox}. We believe that tetra-amide ligand framework is not conducive enough for the stabilization of Cu^{III} species to a larger extent. This assumption is adequately supported by the crystallographic results which exhibits much longer $Cu-N_{amide}$ bond distances in **2** than its nickel analogue **1**. Therefore, Cu^{II} ion requires a considerable metal-ligand bond reduction for the stabilization of Cu^{III} state and as a consequence ejection of an electron is easier generating the Cu^{II} -Ligand(•) radical species.

Fig. 8. Absorption spectrum of one-electron electrochemically oxidized species **2**^{Ox} (red trace) and its comparison with complex **2** (black trace). Both spectra were recorded in DMF. See the text for details.

Conclusions

In this work, a tetra-amide ligand appended with 3-pyridyl groups has been utilized for the synthesis of nickel (**1**) and copper (**2**) complexes. In both cases, tetra-amide ligand enforced a square-planar geometry around the metal coordinated by four $N_{amidate}$ groups. Both complexes exhibited interesting solid-state sheet-like structure wherein complex anions are coordinated to sodium ions via O_{amide} and 3-pyridyl groups. The cyclic voltammetric studies illustrated reversible $M^{3+/2+}$ redox responses at moderate positive potentials. Such moderate redox responses allowed one-electron oxidation generating meta-stable **1**^{Ox} and **2**^{Ox} species exhibiting unique absorption spectral features.

Acknowledgement

RG sincerely thanks Council of Scientific & Industrial Research (CSIR), New Delhi and the University of Delhi for the financial support. Authors thank CIF-USIC of this university for the instrumental facilities and X-ray data collection. DB acknowledges UGC, New Delhi for the SRF fellowship.

Supplementary data

Crystallographic data for complexes **1** and **2** have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, CCDC numbers 1434050 and 1434051.

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